

Chemometric modeling on the aromatic sulfonamides inhibitors of the human *trans* membrane carbonic anhydrase isozymes XIV by CoMFA

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Abstract : The ubiquitous metalloenzymes carbonic anhydrase (CAs, EC4.2.1.1) catalyze the interconversion between carbon dioxide and the bicarbonate ion at the physiological pH. The carbonic anhydrase XIV of extracellular isozyme is highly abundant in neurons and axons in the murine and human brain, where it seems to play an important role in modulating excitatory synaptic transmission. Ligand-based quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) studies were performed on aromatic sulfonamides derivatives as a potential inhibitor of the human *trans* membrane carbonic anhydrase isozyme hCA XIV by comparative molecular field analysis (CoMFA) implemented in the SYBYL packages. The predictive ability of the model was assessed using a test set of five compounds. The best model has demonstrated a good fit having predictive r^2 value of 0.796 and cross validated coefficient q^2 value as 0.59 in tripos CoMFA region. Our results indicate that the steric and electrostatic factors play a significant role in CA XIV inhibition for the investigated compounds.

Keywords : 3D-QSAR, CoMFA, carbonic anhydrase inhibitor, sulfonamides isozymes XIV.

Introduction

In mammals, 16 different α -CA isozymes or CA-related proteins (CARP) were described so far, with very different catalytic activity, sub-cellular localization, tissue distribution and susceptibility to be inhibited by sulfonamides^{1-5,7,8}. Basically, there are several cytosolic forms (CA I-III, CA VII), five membrane-bound isozymes (CA IV, CA IX, CA XII, CA XIV and CA XV), two mitochondrial forms (CA VA and VB), as well as one secreted CA isozyme, CA VI. Then a catalytic isozymes (CARPs) are CA VIII, CA X and CA XI¹⁻⁷. These enzymes are involved in crucial physiological processes connected with respiration and transport of CO₂/bicarbonate between metabolizing tissues and lungs, pH and CO₂ homeostasis, electrolyte secretion in a variety of tissues/organs, biosynthetic reactions (such as gluconeogenesis, lipogenesis and ureagenesis), bone resorption, calcification, tumorigenicity and many other physiologic/pathologic processes¹⁻⁷.

Out of the known mammalian isoforms, the isozyme hCA XIV was one of the last to be discovered, by Nishimori's group in 1999⁸. It has been subsequently

reported that hCA XIV is highly abundant in the brain, kidney, urinary bladder, liver etc.^{9,10}. Many CA isozymes are drug gable targets, and their inhibitors may have applications in the design of antiglaucoma, antitumor, anti-convulsant or antiobesity agents among others¹¹⁻¹³. At this stage it is worth mentioning that the sulfonamides substituted at the sulfamoyl moiety (ArSO₂NHR) are known for about 70 years as antibacterial agents. In the last years, there have been many studies regarding the inhibitory effect of unsubstituted sulfonamides (ArSO₂NH₂) on various CA isozymes. Supuran *et al.*¹⁴ reported for the first inhibition study of the transmembrane isozyme CA XIV with a library of sulfonamides. We report here a QSARs study for the inhibition of human CA XIV with a series of aromatic sulfonamides investigated earlier¹⁴.

3D quantitative structure-activity relationship (3D-QSAR) studies have been found to be of great importance to design and develop potent drugs. Comparative molecular field analysis (CoMFA) used for the 3D-QSAR methodology correlates the biological activity of a series of molecules with their 3D shape and their electrostatic

and steric characteristics. Thus, attempts have been made to design and develop potent inhibitors for the CA XIV inhibitors for the treatment of epilepsy, synaptic efficiency. QSAR finds the parameters of the compounds that govern their biological activities and throw the light on their mechanism of action. Both these aspects of QSAR greatly help modify the structures of the compounds leading to compounds of high therapeutic value¹⁵⁻²¹.

Materials and methodology :

Calibration set (experimental data) :

Supuran *et al.*¹⁴ has reported the inhibition study against hCA XIV with a series of aromatic sulfonamides. The set of 19 sulfonamide and their inhibitory activities against hCA XIV is presented in table. The enzyme inhibition

data K_I values in the nanomolar (nM) range were converted in "A" according to the formula $A = \log (10000/K_I)$ and subsequently, used as the dependent variable for 3D-QSAR study (Table 1). The inhibitory activity (A) value of the molecules under the study spanned a wide range from 0 to 3.

Validation set (test set) :

For the validation of the method, we have proceeded to a QSAR study with a validation set (test set) and reduced calibration set (training set). The test set was extracted from the homogenized calibration set. For the present work, the selection of the test set was done based on the hierarchical clustering technique²². Cluster analysis is a method of arranging objects into groups. In the

Table 1. Structural detail and CA hCA XIV inhibitory activities (in nM and $A = \log 10000/K_I$), estimated activities of the calibration set molecules 1-19

Compd.	n	R	hCA XIV (nm)	Obs. (A)	Est. (A)
1	0	CH ₃ CO	4200	0.38	0.665
2	0	CF ₃ CO	1430	0.84	0.698
3	0	EtCO	3700	0.43	0.672
4	0	<i>n</i> -PrCO	2350	0.63	0.692
5	0	<i>i</i> -PrCO	2400	0.62	0.622
6	0	<i>n</i> -BuCO	2300	0.64	0.786
7	0	<i>t</i> -BuCO	2650	0.58	0.677
8	0	PhCO	1345	0.87	0.759
9	0	MeSO ₂	1250	0.90	0.702
10	0	PhSO ₂	935	1.03	1.023
11	0	4-AcNHC ₆ H ₄ SO ₂	880	1.06	0.949
12	1	PhSO ₂	465	1.30	1.385
13	1	PhNH-C(=S)	237	1.62	1.302
14	2	PhNH-C(=S)	203	1.69	1.868
15	2	PhNH-C(=O)	260	1.59	1.690
16	2	4-H ₂ NO ₂ SC ₆ H ₄ NH-C(=S)	85	2.07	2.124
17	2	4-H ₂ NO ₂ SC ₆ H ₄ CO	79	2.10	1.975
18	2	PhNH-C(=O)	1450	0.84	1.055
19	2	PhNH-C(=O)	430	1.37	0.945

present work, the molecules with rank 3, 6, 12, 16 and 18 have constituted the test set and the remaining as the training set. The test set of seven molecules (25% of database) has captured all the features and spans the activity range of the entire dataset. The series of inhibitory activity (*A*) values and compounds chosen to be part of the training and test sets are listed in Tables 2 and 3.

Template selection and alignment :

In the development of the 3D-QSAR models, the choice of the template conformation is important to provide the illustration of a reliable pharmacophore model. Compound no. **17** was selected as a molecular template. This compound was chosen mainly for its importance as a lead structure; in addition, compound no. **17** is one of the most potent inhibitors of hCA XIV. There are three different methods of alignment in the CoMFA viz. Multifit, Atom fit and Database. I have used database alignment in the CoMFA study on hCA XIV inhibitor.

Table 2. Observed, estimated values of CA hCa XIV inhibitory activity (*A*) for the molecules used in the Training set for CoMFA (Tripos standard region)

Compd.	Obs.	Est.
1	0.38	0.740
2	0.84	0.734
4	0.63	0.768
5	0.62	0.678
7	0.58	0.90
8	0.87	0.791
9	0.90	0.753
10	1.03	1.037
11	1.06	1.045
13	1.62	1.349
14	1.69	1.8111
15	1.59	1.754
17	2.10	2.087
19	1.37	1.045

Table 3. Observed and estimated values of CA hCa XIV inhibitory activity (*A*) for the molecules used in the Test set for CoMFA (Tripos region)

Compd.	Obs.	Est.
3	0.43	0.770
6	0.64	0.904
12	1.30	1.398
16	2.07	1.782
18	0.84	1.121

CoMFA :

The initial CoMFA model was calculated using the Sybyl 7.2 molecular modeling software, for the calculation of charges, the Gastiger-Hückel method was used as implemented in Sybyl 7.2.

The aligned data set molecules were placed in a 3D grid box, such that a entire set was included in it, CoMFA fields were generated using sp³ carbon probe atom carrying +1 charge to generate steric (Lennard-Jones) 6-12 potential, and electrostatic (coulombic potential) fields at each grid point. The steric and electrostatic energy values in CoMFA were truncated at 30 kcal/mol. The CoMFA fields were scaled standard Tripos CoMFA. The CoMFA fields with observed biological activity (*A*) were included in a molecules spread sheet and Partial Least Square (PLS)²³ method was applied to generate 3D-QSAR models. The PLS algorithm with the leave-one-out²⁴ cross-validation method was employed to choose optimum number of component and assess the statistical significance of each model. All cross-validation PLS analyses were performed with a column filters values of 2.0.

The cross-validated coefficient, q^2 was calculated using

$$q^2 (r_{cv}^2) = 1 - \frac{\sum (Y_{\text{predicted}} - Y_{\text{observed}})^2}{\sum (Y_{\text{observed}} - Y_{\text{mean}})^2} \quad (1)$$

where $Y_{\text{predicted}}$, Y_{observed} and Y_{mean} are predicted, actual and mean values of the target inhibitory activity (*A*) respectively.

The optimum number of components was chosen which gave less standard error of prediction and high r_{cv}^2 . In addition; the r_{cv}^2 and number of components, the conventional correlation coefficient r^2 and its standard error were also computed for model. The predictive r^2 (r_{pred}^2) value was calculated using

$$r_{\text{pred}}^2 = SD - \text{PRESS}/SD \quad (2)$$

where SD is the sum of squared deviation between biological activity of the test set and mean activity of training set molecules, and PRESS is the sum of squared deviation between the actual and the predicted activity values for every molecule in the test set. The CoMFA results were graphically interpreted by field contribution maps, using the standard deviation \times coefficient : field

type. The used statistical method does not identify outlier molecules in calibration set.

Results and discussion

The CoMFA 3D-QSAR methods are used on the assumption that the changes in binding affinities of ligands are related to changes in molecular properties represented by fields. The alignment rule and the bioactive conformation are crucial variables in any 3D-QSAR analysis as both will affect outcome of statistical analysis. We have used database alignment in the study and compound no. 17 was used a template for the molecules. The best fit conformation and sub structure used for alignment are shown in Fig. 1.

CoMFA 3D-QSAR analysis :

Steric and electrostatics CoMFA fields were generated using standard procedure. The calibration set of 19 modulators was aligned (Fig. 2) to derive the conventional CoMFA models. Thus, one model was generated, with template molecule using database alignment rule. In this study, we have used the default CoMFA setting, which included both steric and electrostatic fields, and use by alignment in Tripos standard region. The leave-one-out

Fig. 1. Best fit conformation.

Fig. 2. Alignment of molecule in database.

(LOO) cross-validated PLS analysis of the best model gave rise to a cross-validated value (q^2) of 0.693 at 1 component suggesting that the model is a useful tool for predicting Ca XIV inhibitory activity. The correlation coefficient between the calculated and experimental activities of non cross validated value (r^2) of 0.871 with standard error 0.196 indicates that the fitness of analyzed results is 90% compared to experimental results. The steric and electrostatic fields contribution of the model is (43 : 57), indicating that the contribution of steric fields and electrostatics both are requirement on ligand fields interaction.

The statistical parameters of CoMFA analysis of calibration set compounds are summarized in Table 4. Based on the above observation, the best CoMFA model obtained with database alignment was then chosen for further analysis. The observed and estimated inhibitory activity (A) values of the calibration set are shown in Table 1. The correlation of observed vs estimated inhibitory activity of the calibration set are shown in Fig. 5.

Predictive ability of CoMFA models :

The predictive ability of CoMFA models can be evaluated based on q^2 , the cross-validated leave-one-out correlation coefficient, which quantifies the predictive ability of the model. Models are considered to be good predictive power when q^2 is greater than 0.5. A test set was to further validate the predictive power of CoMFA models, a predictive r^2 value (pred- r^2). In the presence of the test set, we obtained the 3D-QSAR CoMFA model for the training set (for 14 molecules); predicted results are summarized in the Table 4. The Table 4 exhibit the q^2 and r^2_{pred} are 0.599 and 0.796 respectively, so the 3D-QSAR model should be suitable for the design of new CA XIV inhibitors. The observed and estimated inhibitory activity (A) values of test set are shown in Table 2. We can state that the estimated value for the molecules in the test set (validation set) are close to the CA XIV experimental inhibitory value and has ordered the molecules in a sequence similar enough to the real one inhibitory value. The correlation of observed vs estimated inhibitory activity of the training and test set are shown in Fig. 6.

The contour map of CoMFA divided in region :

The CoMFA steric field, the green (sterically favorable) and yellow (sterically unfavorable) contour's represent 80% and 20% level contribution shown in Fig.

Table 4. Summary of 3D-QSAR analysis on CA XIV inhibitors of CoMFA on Tripos Standard Region

PLS statistics	Calibration set (all compounds)	Training set
q^2 (leave-one-out cross-validated predicted power of model r^2_{cv})	0.693	0.59
R^2 (correlation coefficient squared of PLS analysis)	0.871	0.873
N (optimum number of components obtained from cross-validated PLS analysis and the same used in final non cross-validated analysis)	1	1
SEE (standard error of estimate)	0.196	0.188
F-test value (F-value)	115.222	82.369
Steric field contribution from CoMFA	0.43	0.45
Electrostatic field contribution from CoMFA	0.57	0.55
Predictive r^2 (r^2_{pred})		0.796

3. The red (negative charge favorable) and blue (positive charge favorable) contours in the CoMFA electrostatic field also represent 20% and 80% level contribution shown in Fig. 4.

The steric and electrostatic contour map elucidate the CoMFA models with the highly active inhibitor compound no. 17 ($A = 2.01$) as a reference. The steric contour map for the CoMFA model Fig. 3 shows that one region at benzene ring positions (substituted benzene ring) has been identified with green polyhedron, which indicate that bulky substituent at these positions may improve the activities. So addition of a bulky group at this position is favorable to the inhibitory activity. The greater values of bioactivity measurement are correlated with more bulk near green, less bulk near yellow.

The electrostatic contour map for the CoMFA models Fig. 4 shows that one regions of the benzene ring positions have been identified with blue polyhedron, which indicate that the electropositive groups at these positions may improve the activities and the big red region over the substitution shows that the electronegative group at

Fig. 6. Observed versus estimated inhibitory activity (A) of Training set and test set.

this position may also improve the activity. So the Fig. 4 indicates that the more positive charge near blue and more negative charge near red, favorable to the binding affinities.

Conclusions

This is the first study which evidenced by means of 3D-QSAR calculations specific features for the inhibition of CA XIV in its interaction with sulfonamide inhibitors. The developed model possesses promising predictive ability as discerned by the test set of 5 compounds which were not included in Training set. So, the model should be useful to explain the relationship between compound structures and biological activities and to facilitate design of more potent compounds as CA XIV inhibitors. The contour plots provided many useful insights into relationships between structural features and inhibitory activity and also give a picture of the main chemical features responsible for the significant inhibitory activity. The steric and electrostatic fields were shown to be the most important parameters controlling the inhibitory activity. These fields identified the functional group and atoms possibly related to the binding and inhibition. Thus, the proposed models can be used to predict the biological activity of compounds before their actual biological testing and provide some insight into structural features for screening of compounds for CA XIV inhibitory activities in early drug development stage.

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